

The Use of Liraglutide Compared to Lifestyle Modifications in Weight Reduction in Lifestyle Clinic Patients: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Background: Liraglutide has been shown to be a successful medication in treating type 2 diabetes (T2D) in clinical trials. Numerous research has looked into the usefulness of liraglutide in the real world for weight loss. **Objectives:** To determine the effectiveness and overall impact of using liraglutide compared to lifestyle modifications in weight reduction. **Methods:** PubMed, SCOPUS, Web of Science, and Science Direct were systematically searched for relevant literature. Rayyan QRCI was employed throughout this comprehensive process. **Results:** Our results included six studies with a total of 611 obese patients receiving liraglutide. Obese patients receiving liraglutide medication may see more notable improvements in visceral fat area, and subcutaneous fat area of the abdomen than those receiving a lifestyle intervention. It was also reported to have a good effect on the cardiovascular system and to be the treatment of choice for weight reduction in patients with T2D. **Conclusion:** Liraglutide-induced weight loss is just as effective as planned lifestyle interventions in obese patients. Additionally, throughout treatment, this therapy improves cardiometabolic indices. More high-quality trials and larger sample sizes are required to fully explore the safety and effectiveness of liraglutide in obese people.

Keywords: *Liraglutide, Weight reduction, Obesity, Lifestyle modifications, Systematic review.*

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Introduction

Obesity is a chronic condition that has detrimental effects on one's health; it can increase the risk of developing type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, as well as increase the likelihood of developing insulin resistance, hypertension, and dyslipidemia (Nestor, et al., 2022; Bradley, et al., 2021; van Ruiten, et al., (2022). It can also shorten life expectancy.

Obesity has recently been linked to an increase in hospitalizations, the requirement for mechanical ventilation, and patient deaths in coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) (Berkovic, et al., 2022). It has been demonstrated that weight loss of 5% to 10% lowers obesity-related complications and enhances the quality of life (Muratori, et al., 2022). However, lifestyle changes by themselves rarely result in weight loss that is sustained (Alabduljabbar, Al-Najim, & le Roux, 2022).

Comprehensive lifestyle modification is one of the main strategies advised for achieving clinically significant weight loss (5%–10% decrease from baseline). To assist patients in adjusting to new dietary and exercise habits, dietitians or other qualified healthcare professionals offer a comprehensive lifestyle counselling program (Leung, et al., 2019). However, only a small percentage of obese patients who undergo lifestyle modification actually lose weight in a clinically meaningful way. It is crucial to identify the predictors of success in order to direct treatment development and identify patients who would benefit from additional support or an alternative weight-loss strategy (Moran, et al., 2019).

Adjunctive medicinal therapy is advised by clinical recommendations, particularly for those with a BMI of 30 or higher or those who have comorbidities of 27 or higher (Wharton, et al., 2020). Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RA) mimic natural glucagon to activate GLP-1 receptors, increase insulin secretion, inhibit glucagon secretion in a glucose concentration-dependent manner, and delay gastric emptying. By reducing food intake through central appetite suppression, weight loss results in addition to lowering blood sugar levels (Nauck, et al., 2021).

Currently, there is no systematic review that compares the results of lifestyle interventions and liraglutide on weight reduction. This review will assess the recently published randomized control trials (RCTs) on both lifestyle modifications and medication (liraglutide).

A systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Xie *et al.* (2022). to assess the effectiveness and safety of liraglutide on weight loss in patients with obesity or overweight in China. They reported that in patients with obesity or overweight, Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1 RAs) were more effective than a placebo in terms of efficacy.

Aim

Our aim in this study is to determine the effectiveness and overall impact of using liraglutide compared to lifestyle modifications in weight reduction.

Objectives

- To compare the results of patients using liraglutide and patients following lifestyle modifications in weight reduction.
- To establish the level of satisfaction in both groups.

Methodology

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with accepted standards (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses, PRISMA) (Page, et al., 2021).

Study Duration

Between January and February 2024.

Study Condition

The aim of this systematic review is to compare the results of the control trials that investigated the effects of lifestyle interventions and liraglutide on weight reduction.

Search Strategy

A thorough search of five major databases was implemented to find the relevant literature, including PubMed, Web of Science, Science Direct, EBSCO, Scopus, and Cochrane Library. We will restrict our search to English and consider each database's unique requirements. The following keywords were converted into PubMed Mesh terms and used to find the relevant studies; "Weight reduction," "Overweight," "Obesity," "Liraglutide," "GLP-1RA," "Lifestyle," and "Diet and exercise." The Boolean operators "OR" and "AND" were used to match the required keywords. Publications with full English text, available free articles, and human trials were among the search results.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- We will only include RCTs to support our comparison.
- Studies that investigate the effect of liraglutide specifically on weight reduction.
- Studies that investigate the effect of lifestyle interventions on weight reduction.

Exclusion criteria

- Participants younger than 18 years.
- Studies in a language other than English.

Data Extraction

In order to find duplicates in the search strategy's output, we used Rayyan (QCRI) (Ouzzani, et al., 2016). The researchers minimized the combined search results based on a set of inclusion/exclusion criteria to determine the relevance of the titles and abstracts. The papers that meet the criteria for inclusion were thoroughly read by the reviewers. Techniques for resolving disputes were discussed by the authors. The approved study was uploaded using a created data extraction form. The authors extracted data about the study titles, authors, study year, study designs, country, population type, participant number, mean age, gender, follow-up duration, the dose of liraglutide, the lifestyle modification used, and main outcomes.

Strategy for Data Synthesis

In order to provide a qualitative review of the included study components and outcomes, summary tables were created using the data collected from the relevant studies. After data extraction for the systematic review, the best strategy to use the information from the included study articles was chosen. Studies that meet the full-text inclusion criteria but do not provide data on the effect of liraglutide and lifestyle interventions on weight reduction were excluded.

Search results

A total of 101 study articles resulted from the systematic search, and 33 duplicates were deleted. Title and abstract screening were conducted on 68 studies, and 52 studies were excluded. 16 reports were sought for retrieval, and 2 articles were not retrieved. Finally, 14 studies were screened for full-text assessment; 5 were excluded for wrong study outcomes, 2 for the wrong population type, and only one article was a letter to the editor. Six eligible study articles were included in this systematic review. A summary of the study selection process is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flowchart Summarizes the Study Selection Process

Characteristics of the Included Studies

Table (1) presents the sociodemographic characteristics of the included study articles. Our results included six studies with a total of 611 obese patients receiving liraglutide. The six studies were RCTs (Khoo, et al., 2017; Yu, et al., 2022; Simeone, et al., 2022; Khoo, et al., 2019; Simeone, et al., 2018; Wadden, et al., 2013). Three studies were conducted in Italy (Yu, et al., 2022; Simeone, et al., 2022; Simeone, et al., 2018), two in Singapore (Khoo, et al., 2017; Khoo, et al., 2019), and one in the USA (Wadden, et al., 2013).

Table (2) presents the clinical characteristics. Obese patients receiving liraglutide medication may see more notable improvements in visceral fat area, and subcutaneous fat area of the abdomen than those receiving a lifestyle intervention. It was also reported to have a good effect on the cardiovascular system and to be the treatment of choice for weight reduction in patients with T2D (Tronieri, et al., 2020; Thakur, et al., 2021; Verma, et al., 2020; Kaji, et al., 2020; Li, et al., 2019; Kanwal, & AlEmadi, 2021).

Table 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Included Participants

Study	Study design	City	Participants	Mean age	Gender (Males)
Khoo et al., 2017	RCT	Singapore	24	39.0 ± 8.1	NM
Yu et al., 2022	RCT	Italy	47	51.53 ± 9.11	23 (48.9)
Simeone et al., 2022	RCT	Italy	53	55	28 (52.8)
Khoo et al., 2019	RCT	Singapore	30	38.6 ± 8.2	NM
Simeone et al., 2018	RCT	Italy	35	55.5	19 (54.3)
Wadden et al., 2013	RCT	USA	422	45.9 ± 11.9	78 (18.5)

Table 2. Clinical Characteristics and Outcomes of the Included Studies

Study	Type of patient	Follow-up duration (weeks)	Liraglutide dose	Main outcomes
Khoo et al., 2017	Obese patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease	26	3 mg daily	For obese Asian adults, liraglutide (3 mg)-induced weight loss is equally effective at reducing the severity of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) as a structured lifestyle intervention.
Yu et al., 2022	People with obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus	12	NM	Patients receiving liraglutide medication may see more notable improvements in hemoglobin A1c, visceral fat area, and subcutaneous fat area of the abdomen than those receiving a lifestyle intervention. Additionally, the rate of adverse events associated with liraglutide use was low. For people with obesity and type 2 diabetes, liraglutide may be the best medication option for managing weight and reducing the distribution of belly fat.
Simeone et al., 2022	People with obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus	3	0.6 mg per day	Treatment with liraglutide was linked to a noteworthy 9% decrease in sST2 levels; interestingly, no effect was seen in individuals who lost the same amount of weight by lifestyle modification.
Khoo et al., 2019	Obese patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease	22	started at 0.6 mg daily and increased by 0.6 mg weekly until 3 mg was reached at the end of 4 weeks and maintained for the next 22 weeks	In obese people with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), liraglutide proved beneficial in reducing weight, hepatic steatosis, and hepatocellular apoptosis; however, unlike lifestyle management, these effects did not last when the medication was stopped.
Simeone et al., 2018	Obese with prediabetes or early T2D	24	0.6 mg per day during the first week, 1.2 mg daily (second week), and 1.8 mg daily	A substantial drop in TX-dependent platelet activation is linked to successful weight loss, whether it be through incretin-based medication or lifestyle modifications. This reduction may be partially mediated by a reduction in inflammation and lipid peroxidation.

			(third week),	
Wadden et al., 2013	Obese individuals without diabetes	56	3 mg daily	Over a 56-week period, liraglutide combined with food and exercise sustained weight loss from calorie restriction and caused further weight loss. There were also improvements in a few cardiovascular disease risk factors.

Discussion

An agonist of the GLP-1 receptor is ligandulite (Tronieri, et al., 2020). It is well known that enteroendocrine L cells found in the distal jejunum and ileum of the colon release the hormone GLP-1, which is then activated following the consumption of food (Thakur, et al., 2021). GLP-1 receptor agonists have been shown to lower cardiovascular events in T2D patients and are also advised as a weight-loss therapy (Verma, et al., 2020). By reducing the decline in the anorexigenic hormone leptin that causes this decline, GLP-1 receptors are linked to weight loss (Kaji, et al., 2020). As a result, it has been noted that while GLP-1 can raise energy expenditure, its impact on weight is linked to a reduction in calorie intake due to local gastrointestinal effects and variables involving the brain's reward centers for appetite (Li, et al., 2019).

In this review, obese patients receiving liraglutide medication may see more notable improvements in visceral fat area, and subcutaneous fat area of the abdomen than those receiving a lifestyle intervention. It was also reported to have a good effect on the cardiovascular system and to be the treatment of choice for weight reduction in patients with T2D (Tronieri, et al., 2020; Thakur, et al., 2021; Verma, et al., 2020; Kaji, et al., 2020; Li, et al., 2019; Kanwal, & AlEmadi, 2021). Kanwal *et al.* conducted a comprehensive systematic review to assess the effectiveness, safety, and use of all liraglutide doses for managing weight in obese non-diabetic individuals in Qatar. They found that liraglutide is effective at reducing weight in non-diabetic, obese people at all doses, but dose 3.0 is the most successful. Liraglutide is generally safe for the majority of study participants, with only minor gastrointestinal side effects. The only issue is the rare but serious adverse events it is associated with (Kanwal, & AlEmadi, 2021).

A critical review reported that in a group of obese patients with conditions such as hypertension, dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes, and obstructive sleep apnea, liraglutide had been shown to be effective at causing and maintaining weight loss. According to comparative data, weight loss with liraglutide is greater than that with orlistat or lorcaserin but a little less than that with phentermine/topiramate combination therapy. For a weight loss indication, more research is required to ascertain its long-term effects, including its effects on cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, in a large and diverse population of people of different races and ethnicities. For the time being, liraglutide is still a critical component of the doctor's toolkit for addressing the expanding obesity epidemic in the US and around the world (Mehta, Marso, & Neeland, 2017).

Another systematic review reported that the individual study findings show that using liraglutide causes weight loss. However, the results of this systematic review demonstrate that there is no statistically significant evidence of study heterogeneity (Hernández Rodríguez, Monroy Sánchez, & Porras Ramírez, 2021). Zhang et al. also reported that liraglutide had been shown to be a reliable and secure method of treating obesity in non-diabetic people in China (Zhang, et al., 2019). Regarding the role of lifestyle interventions in weight reduction, a systematic review found that the most weight was lost with overall lifestyle interventions that included both diet and exercise components. When compared to minimal or standard care, lifestyle interventions for weight loss in adults with severe obesity were found to produce greater weight loss, particularly when diet and exercise were combined (Hassan, et al., 2016).

Chopra *et al.*, (2021) Greater initial weight loss was the most significant predictor of a successful weight loss outcome, according to the most recent literature among subjects undergoing lifestyle interventions. It has also been reaffirmed that factors specific to the patient (being a male, being older, and having existing cardiometabolic risk factors) and those specific to the intervention (having higher adherence and attendance) both play a part in achieving clinically significant weight loss. However, some ideas regarding the function of predictors are still not fully understood, including the interactions between various predictors, their effects on various patterns of weight loss, and the evaluation and management of the predictors to produce successful weight loss outcomes.

A systematic review aimed to evaluate the efficacy of long-term lifestyle interventions for adult prevention of morbidity and weight gain. When it comes to adults who are normal weight, overweight, or obese, prevention of weight gain is crucial. When compared to a no-treatment control group for at least two years, diet demonstrated a significant reduction in weight and improvement in metabolic syndrome and diabetes (Brown, et al., 2009).

We have noted a number of restrictions. First, this review is limited by its qualitative assessment. Secondly, there were variations in the liraglutide starting and maintenance doses. We did not discover any variations in the effects of weight reduction across dosages of liraglutide that were higher or lower. Thirdly, the duration of follow-up varied between the research. Lastly, patients in each study have different medical conditions.

Conclusion

Liraglutide-induced weight loss is just as effective as planned lifestyle interventions in obese patients. Additionally, throughout treatment, this therapy improves cardiometabolic indices. More high-quality trials and larger sample sizes are required to fully explore the safety and effectiveness of liraglutide in obese people.

Budget

Self-funded.

Time Table

Task	Time
Proposal	By the end of June 2023
Manuscript writing	By the end of Jan 2024
Publication	By the end of Feb 2024

References

Alabduljabbar, K., Al-Najim, W., & le Roux, C. W. (2022). The impact once-weekly semaglutide 2.4 mg will have on clinical practice: A focus on the STEP trials. *Nutrients*, *14*(11), Article 2217. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14112217>

Berkovic, M. C., Rezić, T., Bilic-Curcic, I., & Mrzljak, A. (2022). Semaglutide might be a key for breaking the vicious cycle of metabolically associated fatty liver disease spectrum? *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, *10*(20), 6759–6768. <https://doi.org/10.12998/wjcc.v10.i20.6759>

Bradley, C. L., McMillin, S. M., Hwang, A. Y., & Sherrill, C. H. (2021). High-dose once-weekly semaglutide: A new option for obesity management. *Annals of Pharmacotherapy*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10600280211053867>

Brown, T., Avenell, A., Edmunds, L. D., Moore, H., Whittaker, V., Avery, L., & Summerbell, C. (2009). Systematic review of long-term lifestyle interventions to prevent weight gain and morbidity in adults. *Obesity Reviews*, 10(6), 627–638. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-789X.2009.00641.x>

Chopra, S., Malhotra, A., Ranjan, P., Vikram, N. K., Sarkar, S., Siddhu, A., ... & Kumar, A. (2021). Predictors of successful weight loss outcomes among individuals with obesity undergoing lifestyle interventions: A systematic review. *Obesity Reviews*, 22(3), e13148. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13148>

Hassan, Y., Head, V., Jacob, D., Bachmann, M. O., Diu, S., & Ford, J. (2016). Lifestyle interventions for weight loss in adults with severe obesity: A systematic review. *Clinical Obesity*, 6(6), 395–403. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cob.12165>

Hernández Rodríguez, D. C., Monroy Sánchez, D. C., & Porras Ramírez, A. (2021). Efficacy and safety of liraglutide for weight loss in adults: Systematic review. *Revista Colombiana de Endocrinología, Diabetes & Metabolismo*, 7(4), 250–257. <https://doi.org/10.53853/encr.7.4.651>

Kaji, N., Takagi, Y., Matsuda, S., Takahashi, A., Fujio, S., & Asai, F. (2020). Effects of liraglutide on metabolic syndrome in WBN/Kob diabetic fatty rats supplemented with a high-fat diet. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine*, 3(1), 62–68. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ame2.12112>

Kanwal, S., & AlEmadi, E. A. (2021). Liraglutide for weight management, critical analysis of efficacy and side effects in non-diabetic individuals with obesity: A comprehensive systematic review. *Middle East Journal of Family Medicine*, 19(4), 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.5742/MEWFM.2021.94062>

Khoo, J., Hsiang, J. C., Taneja, R., Koo, S. H., Soon, G. H., Kam, C. J., Law, N. M., & Ang, T. L. (2019). Randomized trial comparing effects of weight loss by liraglutide with lifestyle modification in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *Liver International*, 39(5), 941–949. <https://doi.org/10.1111/liv.14002>

Khoo, J., Hsiang, J., Taneja, R., Law, N. M., & Ang, T. L. (2017). Comparative effects of liraglutide 3 mg vs structured lifestyle modification on body weight, liver fat and liver function in obese patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: A pilot randomized trial. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*, 19(12), 1814–1817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.13022>

Leung, A. W. Y., Chan, R. S. M., Sea, M. M. M., & Woo, J. (2019). Identifying psychological predictors of adherence to a community-based lifestyle modification program for weight loss among Chinese overweight and obese adults. *Nutrition Research and Practice*, 13(5), 415–424. <https://doi.org/10.4162/nrp.2019.13.5.415>

Li, Z., Yang, P., Liang, Y., Xia, N., Li, Y., Su, H., & Pan, H. (2019). Effects of liraglutide on lipolysis and the AC3/PKA/HSL pathway. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*, 12, 1697–1703. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S212682>

Mehta, A., Marso, S. P., & Neeland, I. J. (2017). Liraglutide for weight management: A critical review of the evidence. *Obesity Science & Practice*, 3(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/osp4.84>

Moran, L. J., Noakes, M., Clifton, P., Buckley, J., Brinkworth, G., Thomson, R., & Norman, R. J. (2019). Predictors of lifestyle intervention attrition or weight loss success in women with polycystic ovary syndrome who are overweight or obese. *Nutrients*, 11(3), Article 492. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11030492>

- Muratori, F., Vignati, F., Di Sacco, G., Gavazzi, L., Pellegrino, D., & Del Prete, M. (2022). Efficacy of liraglutide 3.0 mg treatment on weight loss in patients with weight regain after bariatric surgery. *Eating and Weight Disorders - Studies on Anorexia, Bulimia and Obesity*, 27(7), 2775–2781. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40519-022-01420-0>
- Nauck, M. A., Quast, D. R., Wefers, J., & Meier, J. J. (2021). GLP-1 receptor agonists in the treatment of type 2 diabetes—state-of-the-art. *Molecular Metabolism*, 46, Article 101102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmet.2020.101102>
- Nestor, J. J., Parkes, D., Feigh, M., Suschak, J. J., & Harris, M. S. (2022). Effects of ALT-801, a GLP-1 and glucagon receptor dual agonist, in a translational mouse model of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. *Scientific Reports*, 12, Article 6666. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10577-2>
- Ouzzani, M., Hammady, H., Fedorowicz, Z., & Elmagarmid, A. (2016). Rayyan—a web and mobile app for systematic reviews. *Systematic Reviews*, 5, Article 210. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0384-4>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., & Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *International Journal of Surgery*, 88, Article 105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2021.105906>
- Simeone, P., Liani, R., Tripaldi, R., Di Castelnuovo, A., Guagnano, M. T., Tartaro, A., Bonadonna, R. C., Federico, V., Cipollone, F., Consoli, A., & Santilli, F. (2018). Thromboxane-dependent platelet activation in obese subjects with prediabetes or early type 2 diabetes: Effects of liraglutide- or lifestyle changes-induced weight loss. *Nutrients*, 10(12), Article 1872. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu10121872>
- Simeone, P., Tripaldi, R., Michelsen, A., Ueland, T., Liani, R., Ciotti, S., Birkeland, K. I., Gulseth, H. L., Di Castelnuovo, A., Cipollone, F., Aukrust, P., & Santilli, F. (2022). Effects of liraglutide vs. lifestyle changes on soluble suppression of tumorigenesis-2 (sST2) and galectin-3 in obese subjects with prediabetes or type 2 diabetes after comparable weight loss. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*, 21, Article 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12933-022-01469-w>
- Thakur, U., Bhansali, A., Gupta, R., & Rastogi, A. (2021). Liraglutide augments weight loss after laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy: A randomised, double-blind, placebo-control study. *Obesity Surgery*, 31, 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11695-020-04980-0>
- Tronieri, J. S., Fabricatore, A. N., Wadden, T. A., Auerbach, P., Endahl, L., Sugimoto, D., & Rubino, D. (2020). Effects of dietary self-monitoring, physical activity, liraglutide 3.0 mg, and placebo on weight loss in the SCALE IBT Trial. *Obesity Facts*, 13(6), 572–583. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000511497>
- van Ruiten, C. C., Smits, M. M., Kok, M. D., Serné, E. H., van Raalte, D. H., Kramer, M. H., & IJzerman, R. G. (2022). Mechanisms underlying the blood pressure lowering effects of dapagliflozin, exenatide, and their combination in people with type 2 diabetes: A secondary analysis of a randomized trial. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*, 21, Article 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12933-022-01457-0>
- Verma, S., McGuire, D. K., Bain, S. C., Bhatt, D. L., Leiter, L. A., Mazer, C. D., Pratley, R. E., Rasmussen, S., Buse, J. B., & Holst, A. G. (2020). Effects of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists liraglutide and semaglutide on cardiovascular and renal outcomes across body mass index categories in type 2 diabetes: Results of the LEADER and SUSTAIN 6 trials. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*, 22(12), 2487–2492. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.14172>

Wadden, T. A., Hollander, P., Klein, S., Niswender, K., Woo, V., Hale, P. M., & Aronne, L. (2013). Weight maintenance and additional weight loss with liraglutide after low-calorie-diet-induced weight loss: The SCALE Maintenance randomized study. *International Journal of Obesity*, 37(11), 1443–1451. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ijo.2013.120>

Wharton, S., Lau, D. C., Vallis, M., Sharma, A. M., Biertho, L., Campbell-Scherer, D., & Wicklum, S. (2020). Obesity in adults: A clinical practice guideline. *CMAJ*, 192(31), E875–E891. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.191707>

Xie, Z., Yang, S., Deng, W., Li, J., & Chen, J. (2022). Efficacy and safety of liraglutide and semaglutide on weight loss in people with obesity or overweight: A systematic review. *Clinical Epidemiology*, 14, 1463–1476. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CLEP.S384682>

Yu, D., Zou, M., Pan, Q., Song, Y., Li, M., Zhang, X., Zhou, Y., Wang, X., & Guo, L. (2022). Effects of liraglutide or lifestyle interventions combined with other antidiabetic drugs on abdominal fat distribution in people with obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus evaluated by the energy spectrum CT: A prospective randomized controlled study. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 13, 951570. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2022.951570>

Zhang, P., Liu, Y., Ren, Y., Bai, J., Zhang, G., & Cui, Y. (2019). The efficacy and safety of liraglutide in obese, non-diabetic individuals: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *African Health Sciences*, 19(3), 2591–2599. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v19i3.55>

